

COMPUTER SIMULATION OF THE TRANSVERSE CRACKING
PROCESS IN GLASS FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of local variations in fibre volume fraction, and ply geometry on the multiple cracking of $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ epoxy glass laminates have been studied by experimental observation of the cracking sequence. The shear-lag theory has been modified and a computer simulation of the cracking sequence obtained. The local inner ply thickness and fibre volume fraction can determine the most probable locations of the first 10 cracks. For a uniform ply thickness the initial cracks form in fibre rich regions but post-curing can change the location of the first cracks to resin rich areas.

INTRODUCTION

Multiple transverse cracking of $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ crossply laminates has been the subject of much attention over recent years. Composite materials are unique in that first ply failure often occurs in the 90° plies and the subsequent accumulation of damage determines the design parameters. The modified shear lag theory of Bailey et al [1-3] predicts the multiple cracking process by assuming that the transverse ply has a uniform strength and that the cracks form mid-way between previously existing cracks as the applied stress increases. The theory becomes more accurate as the crack density increases since there is a greater probability that the stress

transferred back into the 90° ply will occur mid-way between existing cracks as the crack spacing approaches twice the transfer length. Indeed Manders et al [4] showed that the occurrence of early cracks can be better predicted using a Weibull statistical model. Similarly Jones and Rock [5], in attempting to assess the environmental degradation of transverse strength, demonstrated the increase in the transverse first cracking strain with crack accumulation up to a limiting crack spacing. In all of these studies the first cracking strain was found to vary within a small range of about 10% which is of the same magnitude as the experimental error, which implied that contrary to the view of Wang [6] the cracks resulted from microstructural fluctuations rather than the presence of gross laminate defects such as microcracks.

One facet which has not previously been studied in detail is the effect of inherent local variations in fibre volume fraction and ply dimensions on the cracking pattern. The purpose of the present study was to assess the likelihood of failure of resin or fibre rich regions in the transverse ply which result from differing degrees of tow dispersion which occur during fabrication by filament winding.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminates were fabricated from E-glass fibres (Silenka O84 P - 1200 tex) by dry filament winding onto square frames. The fibres were vacuum impregnated with the epoxy resin formulation (Epikote 828, 80 phr Epikure NMA, 2 phr BDMA). Full details of the technique has been given elsewhere [7]. The laminates were cured for 3 hours at 100°C between release film and glass plates under a pressure of 300 kg cm^{-2} . The coupons ($250 \times 10 \times 2.5\text{ mm}$) were cut from the laminate using a water cooled diamond wheel and post-cured for 3 hours at 100, 125 and 150°C in a chromatography oven ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$).

For tensile testing, acid etched Al end-tags and 10 mm strain gauges were adhered with epoxy resin. The coupons were loaded in an Instron 1196 or 1175 at a displacement rate of 0.05 mm min^{-2} . A photographic record of the transverse cracking sequence was taken at 60 second intervals. The order in which the cracks appeared was also noted. For microscopic analysis the coupons were polished with $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ diamond paste using a detergent/water solution as lubricant and examined by incident and transmitted light using a Zeiss optical photomicroscope.

The residual thermal strain present in the laminates was estimated from the curvature of equivalent unbalanced $0^\circ/90^\circ$ coupons as described elsewhere [8]. The average fibre volume fraction was calculated from the laminate thickness by the method described by Mulheron [8]. The local volume fraction in the transverse ply and the ply thickness was computed geometrically from enlarged optical photomicrographs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental Results

Manders et al [3] concluded that the 90° ply was not of uniform strength and a statistical model provided a better description of the transverse cracking behaviour at 'low' stresses when the cracks were widely spaced. However, the intrinsic variation of 14% appeared smaller than expected for a defect controlled failure process. Indeed a characteristic variation of only 10% was determined for the transverse first cracking strain in the present work as reported elsewhere [9]. One interpretation of this behaviour is that the initial cracks are controlled by inhomogeneities within the transverse ply. A preliminary examination of the polished edges revealed that some of these early cracks were associated with resin rich areas between the glass fibre tows. To investigate whether certain regions were more susceptible to cracking the edge at a transverse ply was examined before and after testing. The location of the damage was compared with local variations in the ply thickness and fibre volume fraction.

A coupon was cut from a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ glass fibre/epoxy laminate and polished along one cut longitudinal edge. A 100 mm gauge length was photographed under incident light in an optical photomicroscope at x 30 magnification. Contact prints were taken from the negatives and joined together in sequence to obtain an enlarged cross section of the transverse ply. The coupon was loaded to 1.4% strain on an Instron 1196, the transverse cracking sequence recorded and the polished edges rephotographed. a second set of contact prints were assembled for comparison with the original. A typical result is given in Fig.1 where the location of individual transverse tows are clearly seen. This illustrates the problem of attaining a uniform fibre distribution within the plies. The crack ranked 56 is associated with a resin rich region whilst 5 passes through an area of above average fibre density. Figure 2a compares the cracking sequence with the variation in inner ply thickness and fibre volume

Table 1

COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL
CRACK LOCATIONS

CRACK NUMBER	LOCATION (mm from coupon edge)	
	EXPERIMENTAL	PREDICTED
1	11	21
2	23	68
3	15	12
4	5	38
5	74	47
6	99	57
7	86	86
8	52	29
9	30	79
10	38	93
11	34	6

Before tensile testing

After tensile testing

CRACK 56

CRACK 5

FIGURE 1

Incident light optical micrographs of a typical section along the transverse ply of a $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ epoxy laminate coupon giving the order in which the cracks formed.

FIGURE 2

Location (O) of the first ten transverse cracks in a (0°/90°/0°) epoxy laminate with respect to the inner ply thickness (upper line) and fibre volume fraction (lower line). a) the experimental locations b) the predicted locations from the computer simulation.

FIGURE 3

The strain transfer function for cracks spaced 3 and 5 mm apart. This has been termed as 'independent' cracking.

fraction along the transverse ply. Although some level of correlation could be observed for the earlier cracks, a meaningful analysis was not possible because of the large variation in the fibre distribution and inner ply thickness. Furthermore, a crack may initiate in a particular region but run into another, making the site of initiation uncertain. It is more likely for a crack to form at a cut-edge rather than in the bulk of the coupon because of the stress fields in these regions. Some of the cracks, therefore, could have been caused by defects or inhomogeneities on the other unexamined edge of the coupon. The speed with which these cracks propagated made it impossible to observe from which edges they originated. Therefore the experiment was repeated but both cut edges were polished and photographed under transmitted light. The distribution of glass fibres could be observed as light and dark areas, the lighter zones representing regions of more densely packed fibres. The mirror imaging of the illumination between opposing cut edges was consistent along the entire length of the coupons and indicated that the fibre/resin distribution was constant across the width of the 90° ply. Furthermore the large majority of transverse cracks ran parallel to each other and the direction of reinforcement. The distribution given in Fig. 2 was therefore considered to be a satisfactory description of the cracking process.

In order therefore to identify how local variations in ply geometry and volume fraction interact to determine the ply failure strain a computer simulation of the cracking process was designed in an attempt to predict the observed cracking sequence.

COMPUTER SIMULATION

The minimum transverse ply failure strain can be calculated from the constraint theory of Bailey et al [2] according to

$$\epsilon_{tu}^{\min} = \left[\frac{2bE_{\ell} \gamma_t \phi^{1/2}}{(b+d)E_t E_c} \right]^{1/2} - \epsilon_{t\ell}^{\text{th}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $\phi = E_c G_t (b+d)/t_{\ell} E_t b d^2$, E_t, E_{ℓ}, E_c are the tensile moduli of the transverse ply, longitudinal ply and composite respectively.

γ_t is the fracture surface energy of the transverse ply,
 $b, 2d$ are the longitudinal and transverse ply thicknesses, and
 $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{\text{th}}$ is the thermal strain in the longitudinal direction of the transverse ply.

A full analysis of the individual expansion coefficients and the

stress free temperature required to calculate $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ has been given previously [8]. The calculations have been further extended to examine the effect of varying the post-cure temperature, inner ply fibre volume fraction, and inner and outer ply thickness on the values of $\epsilon_{t\ell}^{th}$ and ϵ_{tu}^{min} for a coupon of uniform geometry and fibre volume fraction [9]. A value of 190 Nm^{-2} was chosen for γ_t by fitting previously derived experimentally recorded values to equation 1. This value compares favourably with that of 120 Nm^{-2} obtained experimentally by Parvizi [2]. A larger value was expected since the matrix had a higher degree of cure (as shown by a higher glass transition temperature).

In the multiple cracking theory elastic continuity between the longitudinal and transverse plies enables the stress adjacent to the first crack to be transferred back into the longitudinal plies according to equation 2.

$$\Delta\sigma = \Delta\sigma_0 \exp(-\phi^{1/2}y) \quad \dots (2)$$

where y is the distance from the transverse crack

and $\Delta\sigma_0$ is the additional stress on the longitudinal ply at $y = 0$,

which would have been on the transverse ply had there been no crack.

In terms of strain the equation becomes

$$\Delta\epsilon_t = b\Delta\sigma_0 [1 - \exp(-\phi^{1/2}y)]/E_t d \quad \dots (3)$$

This expression defines the magnitude of the strain transferred back into the transverse ply after a crack has occurred at $y = 0$. Thus for another crack to occur the applied stress (σ_a) and hence $\Delta\sigma_0$ must be increased to such a value that the strain in the transverse ply exceeds the transverse ply failure strain within the length of the coupon. When multiple cracking occurs in a coupon the strain fields surrounding the crack will interact depending upon the crack spacing according to the following expression [9]:

$$\Delta\epsilon_t = b\Delta\sigma_0 [1 + \exp(-\phi^{1/2}t) - \exp(-\phi^{1/2}y) - \exp(\phi^{1/2}(y-t))]/E_t d \quad \dots (4)$$

where t = crack spacing.

Figure 3 presents this relationship in terms of the percentage of the original strain remaining in the transverse ply between cracks spaced 3 and 5 mm apart. This effect is termed independent cracking.

One problem in applying this analysis to a real laminate is that the effect of a crack on the surrounding areas of ply is limited to within a finite distance (the stress transfer length). This is approximately 2mm for the system under consideration. Therefore if the crack spacing is greater than 4 mm it is not possible to predict the location of the cracks within

the 90° ply. This can be overcome by dividing the laminate coupon up into a series of elements with discrete cross sections which are assigned specific values of inner and outer ply thickness and fibre volume fraction in order to define a unique failure strain for each element (Fig.4). Transverse cracks are initially assumed to form in the elements with the lowest failure strains but will become increasingly dependent upon the strain redistribution around the cracks as the applied strain increases. The size of the element chosen is critical, it must be small enough to contain only one crack but large enough to present a realistic simulation of the observed variations. In the model the minimum failure strain for each element is calculated according to equation 1. It is assumed that failure occurs when the level of strain present in the element exceeds the failure strain. This is dependent therefore on the nature of the strain transfer function which is difficult to model but a reasonable estimate has been made by considering dependent and independent cracking models. The latter can be described as follows.

Consider a section of ply with an initial applied strain of $\epsilon_{t_0} = 1\%$ (Fig.5), if this cracks the strain will be unloaded onto the longitudinal plies and an amount $\Delta\epsilon_t$ will be transferred back into the transverse ply according to equation 4. This is converted into a simple ratio by:

$$\epsilon_{ta}^y = 1 - ((\epsilon_{t_0} - \Delta\epsilon_t)/\epsilon_{t_0}) \quad \dots (5)$$

The proportion of initial strain remaining in the ply at a point y , after cracking, is therefore:

$$\epsilon_t^y = \epsilon_{ta}^y \times \epsilon_{t_0} \quad \dots (6)$$

As shown in Fig.6 this equation overestimates the experimental crack density at a given applied stress. A better fit to the data could be achieved by modifying the stress transfer function using a squared function (Equation 7.1). The results of this analysis are also given in Fig.6 but the crack density is still overestimated. This form of equation does not take into consideration the interaction between nested transverse cracks. This is designated as 'dependent' cracking as opposed to 'independent' cracking. As shown in Fig.7 dependent cracking becomes significant when a crack forms between two existing cracks in sufficient proximity for the strain to be redistributed back into the partially unloaded region associated with either or both of the earlier cracks. In these regions therefore the level of strain is no longer ϵ_{t_0} but ϵ_t^y . Taking this into account the

strain fields around a series of cracks can be described by

$$\text{First crack} \quad \epsilon_{t_1}^y = \epsilon_{t_0}^y \times (\epsilon_{t_a}^y)^2 \quad \dots \quad (7.1)$$

$$\text{Second crack} \quad \epsilon_{t_2}^y = \epsilon_{t_1}^y \times (\epsilon_{t_a}^y)^2 \quad \dots \quad (7.2)$$

$$\text{Third crack} \quad \epsilon_{t_3}^y = \epsilon_{t_2}^y \times (\epsilon_{t_a}^y)^2 \quad \dots \quad (7.3)$$

etc.

A significantly improved fit to the crack density was achieved with this analysis as shown in Fig.6.

These modifications to the shear lag analysis were incorporated into a computer simulation which was used to determine the onset and location of transverse cracks in several model $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ glass fibre/epoxy laminates. The programme is based on a Monte Carlo type search routine and full details are given elsewhere [9].

1000, 0.1 mm long, elements were generated to represent a laminate coupon (Fig. 4). Every tenth element was assigned a randomly generated value for the inner ply thickness, inner ply fibre volume fraction and the outer ply thickness set between a maximum and minimum value specified for each coupon. The data for the interstitial elements was calculated from a straight line fit between the assigned elements. An element cracking order was predicted using equation 4 as the condition for failure and equation 7 to determine the strain redistribution in the inner ply resulting from the formation of a crack. The set of random data generated for each coupon was identical so that the effect of variations in the input parameters could be compared.

The laminate properties were found to have no affect on the location of cracks ranked greater than 40 at which the crack spacing is approximately 2.5mm. This is understandable in terms of the modified shear log analysis of Garrett, Bailey and Parvizi [1]. The locations of the first ten cracks were however affected by the geometry and curing conditions. For example, as the post-cure temperature increased the locations changed from high fibre volume fraction areas to regions of low fibre volume fraction. Variations in inner ply thickness were also found to be significant. The object of this paper, however, is to compare the experimental data with the results from computer simulation, full details of which will be given elsewhere.

Figure 2b gives the result of the simulation for the first ten cracks of a coupon with approximately equivalent geometry to the experimental coupon in Fig.2a. A qualitative correlation was obtained. To improve on

FIGURE 4

This figure illustrates a section of coupon where the elements have been assigned for use in the computer simulation.

FIGURE 5

The reduction in initial transverse ply strain (ϵ_{t0}) after the formation of a crack according to equations 5^{t0}-7. The difference between a simple Garrett and Bailey approach [1-3] (represented by ϵ_{ta}) and its square is given as $\Delta \epsilon^y$ at a position y along the coupon.

FIGURE 6

Comparison between the crack spacing obtained from experimental and computer generated data.

FIGURE 7

The series of strain transfer functions described by equation 7 and designated as 'dependent' cracking.

this the experimental laminate parameters were entered directly into the computer simulation. The experimental values were taken from photographs and averaged over 1 mm lengths. These were of much lower resolution than the capacity of the computer simulation (0.1 mm) and therefore a considerable amount of inaccuracy would have been introduced. With this in mind, however, the locations of the first ten observed and predicted cracks given in Table 1 present an encouraging quantitative correlation.

CONCLUSIONS

The shear lag analysis with a modified stress transfer function giving full consideration to the interaction between the stress redistribution around the transverse cracks has been shown to give a better prediction of the multiple cracking process in $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminates. In addition, simulation of the cracking sequences using a multi-element model predicts that the early cracks will form in regions of the inner ply in which the local thickness and volume fraction interact to give a lower element strength. For the more practical situation in which a narrow variation in inner ply thickness is encountered the first cracks form in regions of high local fibre volume fraction. Post-curing increases the probability that the cracks will form in resin rich regions due to the increase in thermal strain produced in these areas. From these studies it is demonstrated that the observed variations in transverse strength of model cross ply laminates probably arises from local variations in tow dispersion and ply geometry. Careful control of the fibre dispersion may lead to improved transverse strength and to more durable fibre composites.

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